

ALBUM AND ARTIST EFFECTS FOR AUDIO SIMILARITY AT THE SCALE OF THE WEB

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ABSTRACT

In audio based music recommendation, a well known effect is the dominance of songs from the same artist as the query song in recommendation lists. We verify that this effect also exists in a very large data set at the scale of the world wide web (> 250000). Since our data set contains multiple albums from individual artists, we can also show that the album effect is relatively bigger than the artist effect.

1 INTRODUCTION

In Music Information Retrieval, one of the central goals is to automatically recommend music to users based on a query song or query artist. This can be done using expert knowledge (e.g. `pandora.com`), social meta-data (e.g. `last.fm`), collaborative filtering (e.g. `amazon.com/mp3`) or by extracting information directly from the audio. In audio based music recommendation, a well known effect is the dominance of songs from the same artist as the query song in recommendation lists.

This effect has been studied mainly in the context of genre classification experiments. If songs from the same artist are allowed in both training and test sets, this can lead to over-optimistic results since usually all songs from an artist have the same genre label. It can be argued that in such a scenario one is doing artist classification rather than genre classification. One could even speculate that the specific sound of an album (mastering and production effects) is being classified. In [9] the use of a so-called “artist filter” ensuring that all songs from an artist are in either the training or the test set is proposed. The authors found that the use of such an artist filter can lower the classification results quite considerably (with one of their music collection even from 71% down to 27%). These over-optimistic accuracy results due to not using an artist filter have been confirmed in other studies [7] [1]. Other results suggest that the use of an artist filter not only lowers genre classification accuracy but may also

erode the differences in accuracies between different techniques [2].

All these results were achieved on rather small data bases (from 700 to 15000). Often whole albums from an artist were part of the data base, maybe even more than one. These specifics of the data bases are often unclear and not properly documented. In extending these results, we analyse a very large data set at the scale of the world wide web (> 250000) with multiple albums from individual artists. We try to answer the following questions:

- Is there an album and artist effect even in very large data bases?
- Is the album effect larger than the artist effect?
- What is the influence of the size of a data base on music recommendation and classification?

2 DATA

For our experiments we used a data set $D(ALL)$ of $S = 254398$ song excerpts (30 seconds) from a popular web-shop selling music. The freely available preview song excerpts were obtained with an automated web-crawl. All meta information (artist name, album title, song title, genres) is parsed automatically from the html-code. The excerpts are from $U = 18386$ albums from $A = 1700$ artists. From the 280 existing different hierarchical genres, only the $G = 22$ general ones on top of the hierarchy are being kept for further analysis (e.g. “Pop/General” is kept but not “Pop/Vocal Pop”). The names of the genres plus percentages of songs belonging to each of the genres are given in Tab. 1. Please note that every song is allowed to belong to more than one genre, hence the percentages in Tab. 1 add up to more than 100%. The genre information is identical for all songs on an album. The numbers of genre labels per albums are given in Tab. 2. Our data base was set up so that every artist contributes between 6 to 29 albums (see Tab. 3).

To study the influence of the size of the database on results, we created random non-overlapping splits of the entire data set: $D(1/2)$ - two data sets with mean number of

song excerpts = 127199, $D(1/20)$ - twenty data sets with mean number of songs excerpts = 12719.9, $D(1/100)$ - one hundred data sets with mean number of songs excerpts = 2543.98. An artist with all their albums is always a member of a single data set.

Pop	Classical	Broadway
49.79	12.89	7.45
Soundtracks	Christian/Gospel	New Age
1.00	10.20	2.48
Miscellaneous	Opera/Vocal	Alternative Rock
6.11	3.24	27.13
Rock	Rap/Hip-Hop	R&B
51.78	0.98	4.26
Hard Rock/Metal	Classic Rock	Country
15.85	15.95	4.07
Jazz	Children's Music	International
6.98	7.78	9.69
Latin Music	Folk	Dance & DJ
0.54	11.18	5.24
Blues		
11.24		

Table 1. Percentages of songs belonging to the 22 genres with multiple membership allowed.

# labels	1	2	3	4	5 to 8
percentage	22.74	20.68	29.64	20.62	6.32

Table 2. Percentages of albums having 1,2,3,4 or 5 to 8 genre labels.

# albums	6	7	8	9	10
percentage	0.06	22.88	18.59	11.59	8.35
# albums	11	12	13	14	15
percentage	6.88	6.29	5.59	3.59	3.24
# albums	16	17	18	19	20 to 29
percentage	1.65	1.76	2.35	1.18	6.00

Table 3. Percentages of artists having 6, 7, ..., 20 to 29 albums.

3 METHODS

We compare two approaches based on different parametrisations of the data. Whereas Mel Frequency Cepstrum Coefficients (MFCCs) are a quite direct representation of the

spectral information of a signal and therefore of the specific “sound” or “timbre” of a song, Fluctuation Patterns (FPs) are a more abstract kind of feature describing the amplitude modulation of the loudness per frequency band. It is our hypothesis, that MFCCs are more prone to pick up production and mastering effects of a single album as well as the specific “sound” of an artist (voice, instrumentation, etc).

3.1 Mel Frequency Cepstrum Coefficients and Single Gaussians (G1)

We use the following approach to music similarity based on spectral similarity. For a given music collection of songs, it consists of the following steps:

1. for each song, compute MFCCs for short overlapping frames
2. train a single Gaussian (G1) to model each of the songs
3. compute a similarity matrix between all songs using the symmetrised Kullback-Leibler divergence between respective G1 models

The 30 seconds song excerpts in mp3-format are recomputed to 22050Hz mono audio signals. We divide the raw audio data into non-overlapping frames of short duration and use Mel Frequency Cepstrum Coefficients (MFCC) to represent the spectrum of each frame. MFCCs are a perceptually meaningful and spectrally smoothed representation of audio signals. MFCCs are now a standard technique for computation of spectral similarity in music analysis (see e.g. [4]). The frame size for computation of MFCCs for our experiments was 46.4ms (1024 samples). We used the first 25 MFCCs for all our experiments.

A single Gaussian (G1) with full covariance represents the MFCCs of each song [5]. For two single Gaussians, $p(x) = \mathcal{N}(x; \mu_p, \Sigma_p)$ and $q(x) = \mathcal{N}(x; \mu_q, \Sigma_q)$, the closed form of the Kullback-Leibler divergence is defined as [10]:

$$KL_N(p||q) = \frac{1}{2} \left(\log \left(\frac{\det(\Sigma_p)}{\det(\Sigma_q)} \right) + Tr(\Sigma_p^{-1}\Sigma_q) + (\mu_p - \mu_q)' \Sigma_p^{-1} (\mu_q - \mu_p) - d \right) \quad (1)$$

where $Tr(M)$ denotes the trace of the matrix M , $Tr(M) = \sum_{i=1..n} m_{i,i}$. The divergence is symmetrised by computing:

$$KL_{sym} = \frac{KL_N(p||q) + KL_N(q||p)}{2} \quad (2)$$

3.2 Fluctuation Patterns and Euclidean Distance (FP)

Fluctuation Patterns (FP) [6] [8] describe the amplitude modulation of the loudness per frequency band and are based

on ideas developed in [3]. For a given music collection of songs, computation of music similarity based on FPs consists of the following steps:

1. for each song, compute a Fluctuation Pattern (FP)
2. compute a similarity matrix between all songs using the Euclidean distance of the FP patterns

Closely following the implementation outlined in [7], an FP is computed by: (i) cutting an MFCC spectrogram into three second segments, (ii) using an FFT to compute amplitude modulation frequencies of loudness (range 0 – 10Hz) for each segment and frequency band, (iii) weighting the modulation frequencies based on a model of perceived fluctuation strength, (iv) applying filters to emphasise certain patterns and smooth the result. The resulting FP is a 12 (frequency bands according to 12 critical bands of the Bark scale [11]) times 30 (modulation frequencies, ranging from 0 to 10Hz) matrix for each song. The distance between two FPs i and j is computed as the Euclidean distance:

$$D(FP^i, FP^j) = \sum_{k=1}^{12} \sum_{l=1}^{30} (FP_{k,l}^i - FP_{k,l}^j)^2 \quad (3)$$

4 RESULTS

4.1 Album/Artist Precision

For the full data base $D(ALL)$

For every song in the data base $D(ALL)$, we computed the first nearest neighbour for both methods G1 and FP. For method G1, the first nearest neighbour is the song with minimum Kullback Leibler divergence (Equ. 2) to the query song. For method FP, the first nearest neighbour is the song with minimum Euclidean distance of the FP pattern (Equ. 3) to the query song. We then computed the percentage of instances, where the first nearest neighbour is from the same album (1st AL) or from other albums by the same artist (1st AR) as the query song (see Tab. 4).

For method G1, 27.87% are from the same album and 35.76% from other albums by the same artist. On average, there are 13.46 songs on an album and 131.2 songs from one artist. Considered that there are always more than 250000 songs from other artists, it is quite astonishing that only in 36.37% a song from a different artist turns up as a first nearest neighbour. For method FP, percentages are quite lower with only 2.24% from the same album and 26.85% from other albums by the same artist.

Next we computed the album and artist precision at n . Album precision at n (AL prec) is the percentage of songs from the album in a list of the n nearest neighbours, with

Method	1st AL	1st AR	AL prec	AR prec
G1	27.87	35.76	13.86	8.14
FP	2.24	26.85	0.90	1.63

Table 4. Percentage of first nearest neighbour from same album (1st AL), from other albums from same artist (1st AR), album and artist precision (AL prec, AR prec) for G1 and FP.

Figure 1. Percentage (y-axis) of first nearest neighbour from same album (dashed line), from other albums from same artist (solid) for G1 and different size of data set (x-axis, log-scale).

n being equal to the number of other songs in the same album as the query song. Artist precision at n (AR prec) is the percentage of songs from the artist in a list of the n nearest neighbours, with n being equal to the number of other songs from the same artist as the query song. For $D(ALL)$ and method G1, album precision is at 13.86% and artist precision at 8.14% (see Tab. 4). Precision values for method FP are very small.

To sum up, there is both an album and an artist effect in nearest neighbour based music recommendation for method G1. For this timbre based method, the album effect is even relatively bigger than the artist effect. For method FP, there is only a smaller artist effect but no album effect.

Influence of the size of the data base

We repeated the experiments for all the subsets of the data base as described in Sec. 2. The results depicted in Figs. 1, 2, 3 and 4 show mean values over 100 ($D(1/100)$), 20 ($D(1/20)$), 2 ($D(1/2)$) data sets or the respective single result for the full data set $D(ALL)$. The percentage of the first nearest neighbour from the same album decreases from 38.91% for $D(1/100)$ to 27.82% for $D(ALL)$ for method G1 (Fig. 1). There is a parallel decrease for the first nearest neighbour from other albums from the same artist for

Figure 2. Percentage (y-axis) of first nearest neighbour from same album (dashed line), from other albums from same artist (solid) for FP and different size of data set (x-axis, log-scale).

Figure 4. Precision (y-axis) of album (dashed line) and artist (solid) for FP and different size of data set (x-axis, log-scale).

Figure 3. Precision (y-axis) of album (dashed line) and artist (solid) for G1 and different size of data set (x-axis, log-scale).

method G1 (Fig. 1). A similar decrease at lower levels can be seen for method FP (Fig. 2). As the data sets get larger, the probability that songs from other artists are more similar to the query song than songs from the same album or artist, clearly seems to increase.

Album and artist precision also decrease with increasing size of data set. For method G1, artist precision drops from 35.99% for $D(1/100)$ to 8.14% for $D(ALL)$ even falling below album precision (Fig 3). For method FP, artist precision drops from 19.19% for $D(1/100)$ to 1.63% for $D(ALL)$ which is at the same low level as album precision (Fig. 4).

To sum up, both first nearest neighbour rates and precision values are over estimated when smaller data sets are used.

4.2 Genre Classification

For the full data base $D(ALL)$

We also did experiments on the influence of album and artist filters on genre classification performance. We used nearest neighbour classification as a classifier. For every song in the data base $D(ALL)$, we computed the first nearest neighbour for both methods G1 and FP. For method G1, the first nearest neighbour is the song with minimum Kullback Leibler divergence (Equ. 2) to the query song. For method FP, the first nearest neighbour is the song with minimum Euclidean distance of the FP pattern (Equ. 3) to the query song. When using an album filter (ALF), all other songs from the same album as the query song were excluded from becoming the first nearest neighbour. When using an artist filter (ARF), all other songs from the same artist as the query song were excluded from becoming the first nearest neighbour. When using no filter (NOF), any song was allowed to become the first nearest neighbour. To estimate genre classification accuracy, the genre label of a query song s_{query} and its first nearest neighbour s_{nn} were compared. The accuracy is defined as:

$$acc(s_{query}, s_{nn}) = \frac{|g_{query} \cap g_{nn}|}{\max(|g_{query}|, |g_{nn}|)} \quad (4)$$

with g_{query} (g_{nn}) being a set of all genre labels for the query song (nearest neighbour song) and $|\cdot|$ counting the number of members in a set. Therefore accuracy is defined as the number of shared genre labels divided by the maximum set size of g_{query} and g_{nn} . The latter is done to penalise nearest neighbour songs with high numbers of genre labels. The range of values for accuracy is between 0 and 1. The baseline accuracy achieved by always guessing the three most probable genres (“Rock”, “Pop”, “Alternative Rock”, see Tab. 1) is 37.03%. We decided to use a number

of three genres for this baseline accuracy because the majority of songs is labelled with three genres (see Tab. 2). Average accuracy results for methods G1 and FP are given in Tab. 5. Without using any filter (NOF), G1 clearly outperforms FP (70.69% vs. 46.97%). Using an album filter (ALF) strongly degrades the performance of G1 down to 58.49%, but hardly impairs method FP. Using an artist filter (ARF) further degrades the performance of G1 but also of FP. The difference between G1 and FP is now much closer (39.56% vs. 32.38%). However, method G1 barely outperforms the baseline accuracy of 37.03% and method FP clearly falls below it.

Method	NOF	ALF	ARF
G1	70.69	58.49	39.56
FP	46.97	45.69	32.38

Table 5. Average accuracies for G1 and FP without (NOF) and with album filter (ALF) and artist filter (ARF).

To sum up, not using any filter yields very over-optimistic accuracy results. As a matter fact, results after artist filtering are very close or even below baseline accuracy. There is both an album and an artist filter effect for G1. There is only an album filter effect for FP. Using filters diminishes the differences in accuracies between methods G1 and FP, since filters have a bigger impact on G1 than FP.

Influence of the size of the data base

We repeated the experiments for all the subsets of the data base as described in Sec. 2. The results depicted in Figs. 5 and 6 show mean accuracy values over 100 ($D(1/100)$), 20 ($D(1/20)$), 2 ($D(1/2)$) data sets or the respective single result for the full data set $D(ALL)$. For both methods G1 and FP, the accuracy without using a filter (dotted lines in Figs. 5 and 6) decreases with increasing size of data set. For G1, from 81.66% for $D(1/100)$ to 70.69% for $D(ALL)$. For FP, from 59.24% for $D(1/100)$ to 46.79% for $D(ALL)$. There is an almost parallel decrease in accuracy when using album filters (dashed lines in Figs. 5 and 6). For both methods G1 and FP, the accuracy when using an artist filter (solid lines in Figs. 5 and 6) increases with increasing size of data set. For G1, from 31.28% for $D(1/100)$ to 39.56% for $D(ALL)$. For FP, from 27.19% for $D(1/100)$ to 32.38% for $D(ALL)$.

How can this contrary behaviour of decreasing accuracy for no filter and album filter versus increasing accuracy for artist filters be explained? Larger data sets allow for a larger choice of songs to become the first nearest neighbour. This larger choice of songs can come with the wrong or correct genre labels. If we use artist filters, this larger choice seems to make it more probable that a song with the correct genre label is first nearest neighbour. Otherwise we would not

Figure 5. Accuracy (y-axis) for no filter (dotted line), album filter (dashed line), artist filter (solid) for G1 and different size of data set (x-axis, log-scale).

Figure 6. Accuracy (y-axis) for no filter (dotted line), album filter (dashed line), artist filter (solid) for FP and different size of data set (x-axis, log-scale).

see the increase in accuracy. If we use no filter or only an album filter, the larger choice seems to interfere with the songs from the same artist still in the data base. Songs from the larger choice sometimes end up being first nearest neighbour instead of a song from the same artist as the query song. Since most songs from an artist share the same labels, the larger choice in this case diminishes the accuracy.

To sum up, there clearly is an influence of the data base size on accuracy performance. Small data sets are too pessimistic when artist filters are used. But they are over optimistic if no or only album filters are used.

5 CONCLUSION

There clearly is both an album and an artist effect in music recommendation even in very large data bases. For the timbre based method G1, about one third of the first recom-

mendations are from the same album and about another third from other albums from the same artist as the query song. Considering that every artist has multiple albums in the data base and that an album contains only about 13 songs on average, the album effect is relatively bigger than the artist effect. This suggests that the direct representation of the spectral information is sensitive to production and mastering effects of individual albums. For method FP, there is only a smaller artist effect but no album effect. This suggests that the more abstract signal representation of the fluctuation patterns is not sensitive to production and mastering effects of individual albums. But it is still able to model the common musical sound of an artist across different albums. Please note that we have no way to know whether an artist is working together with the same recording studio or sound engineer for more than one album. Our experiments also show that album and artist effects in music recommendations are over estimated when smaller data sets are being used.

Since most research on artist filters so far concentrated on genre classification, we did large scale experiments on classification accuracy also. We corroborated earlier results that not using any filter yields very over-optimistic accuracy results. Using artist filters even reduces results close to or even below baseline accuracy. As reported before, using artist filters also diminishes the differences in accuracies between methods that are effected distinctly by filtering. Additionally, there clearly is an influence of the data base size on accuracy performance.

As with all large scale performance studies, there remains the question as to how representative and universally valid our results are. We are convinced that our data base is representative of music that is generally listened to and available in the Western hemisphere since it is a large and random subset of about 5 million songs from a popular web-shop. As to the methods employed, we chose one method that closely models the audio signal and one that extracts information on a somewhat higher level. It is our guess that other method's performance will be close to either of our methods depending on their level of closeness to the analysed audio signal. The choice of our methods was also influenced by considerations of computability. After all, 250000 song excerpts are a lot of data to analyse and both our methods can be implemented very efficiently. Using nearest neighbour methods for music recommendation seemed to be the obvious choice.

With audio based music recommendation maturing to the scale of the web, our work provides important insight into the behavior of music similarity for very large data bases. Even with hundreds of thousands of songs, album and artist filtering remain an issue.

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